

OLTINCHI TARTIBLI KOEFFITSIYENTLARI TENG BO'LGAN GIPERBOLIK TIPDAGI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN BOSHLANG'ICH MASALA

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Annotatsiya: *Boshlang'ich masalalar differensial tenglamalar nazariyasining asosiy masalalaridan biridir. Bu masalalarni hal qilish, ayniqsa, tenglama tartibi kattalashib borgan sari qiyinlashib boradi. Ushbu maqolada giperbolik tipdagi oltinchi tartibli maxsus ko'rinishdagi bir tenglama uchun boshlang'ich masala yoritilgan.*

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: *oltinchi tartibli differensial tenglama, giperbolik tipdagi tenglama, boshlang'ich masala, umumiy yechim.*

Ma'lumki, giperbolik tipdagi xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar uchun Koshi masalasini yechish differensial tenglamalar nazariyasining markaziy muammolaridan biridir. Bu muammoni hal etish, ayniqsa tenglama tartibi kattalashib borgan sari qiyinlashib boradi. Quyida biz giperbolik tipdagi oltinchi tartibli maxsus ko'rinishdagi bir tenglama uchun Koshi masalasini o'rganamiz.

$\Omega = \{(x, t) : -\infty < x < +\infty, 0 < t < +\infty\}$ sohada oltinchi tartibli giperbolik tipdagi ushbu

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - a^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right)^3 u(x, t) = 0, (x, t) \in \Omega \quad (1)$$

tenglamani qaraylik, bu yerda $a = \text{const} \neq 0$.

1-Koshi masalasi. Ω sohada (1) tenglamaning

$$\begin{cases} u|_{t=0} = \varphi_0(x), x \in R; & \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}|_{t=0} = 0, x \in R; \\ \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}|_{t=0} = \varphi_1(x), x \in R; & \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial t^3}|_{t=0} = 0, x \in R; \\ \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial t^4}|_{t=0} = \varphi_2(x), x \in R; & \frac{\partial^5 u}{\partial t^5}|_{t=0} = 0, x \in R; \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x, t) \in C^5(\Omega \cup J) \cap C^6(\Omega)$ yechimi topilsin, bu yerda $\varphi_i(x)$, $i = \overline{0, 2}$ – berilgan funksiyalar, $a \neq 0$ – ixtiyoriy haqiqiy son va $J = \{(x, t): t = 0, -\infty < x < +\infty\}$, $R = (-\infty; \infty)$.

Bu masala yechimini topish uchun $u_{tt} - a^2 u_{xx} = U$ belgilash kiritamiz. U holda $\{(1), (2)\}$ masala ushbu

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - a^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = U, & x \in R \\ \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - a^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 U = 0, & x \in R \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

tenglamalar sistemasining

$$\begin{aligned} u|_{t=0} = \varphi_0(x), \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}|_{t=0} = 0, \quad U|_{t=0} = f_1(x), \\ \frac{\partial U}{\partial t}|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial t^2}|_{t=0} = \Phi_1(x), \quad \frac{\partial^3 U}{\partial t^3}|_{t=0} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

(4) boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini topish masalasi bilan almashadi, bu yerda

$$f_1(x) = \varphi_1(x) - a^2 \varphi_0''(x), \quad \Phi_1(x) = \varphi_2(x) - a^2 \varphi_1''(x). \quad (5)$$

(3) va (4) masalani yechish uchun quyidagi lemmadan foydalanamiz:

Lemma. Agar $f(x) \in L_1(\Omega)$ bo'lsa, u holda quyidagi tenglik o'rinli:

$$\int_0^t d\eta \int_{x-a(t-\eta)}^{x+a(t-\eta)} [f(\xi - a\eta) + f(\xi + a\eta)] d\xi = t \int_{x-at}^{x+at} f(s) ds, \quad (6)$$

$$\int_0^t \eta d\eta \int_{x-a(t-\eta)}^{x+a(t-\eta)} d\xi \int_{\xi-a\eta}^{\xi+a\eta} f(s) ds = \frac{t}{4a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2] f(s) ds. \quad (7)$$

Isbot. (6) tenglikning chap qismidagi ichki integralni ikkita integrallar yig'indisi shaklida yozib, integral o'zgaruvchilarini har bir integral uchun mos ravishda $s = \xi - a\eta$ va $s = \xi + a\eta$ kabi almashtiramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \int_0^t d\eta \int_{x-a(t-\eta)}^{x+a(t-\eta)} f(\xi - a\eta) d\xi + \int_0^t d\eta \int_{x-a(t-\eta)}^{x+a(t-\eta)} f(\xi + a\eta) d\xi = \\ &= \int_0^t d\eta \int_{x-at}^{x+at-2a\eta} f(s) ds + \int_0^t d\eta \int_{x-at+2a\eta}^{x+at} f(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Hosil bo'lgan karrali integrallarning η va s o'zgaruvchilari bo'yicha integrallash tartibini almashtirish natijasida quyidagi integrallarga ega bo'lamiz:

$$J = \frac{1}{2a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} (x-s+at) f(s) ds + \frac{1}{2a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} (s-x+at) f(s) ds = t \int_{x-at}^{x+at} f(s) ds.$$

Endi (7) tenglikni isbotlaymiz. (7) tenglikning chap tomonida dastlab, η va ξ bo'yicha, so'ngra η va s bo'yicha integrallash tartibini o'zgartirib, quyidagi tenglikni hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \int_{x-at}^x d\xi \int_0^{\frac{at-x+\xi}{a}} \eta d\eta \int_{\xi-a\eta}^{\xi+a\eta} f(s) ds + \int_x^{x+at} d\xi \int_0^{\frac{at-\xi+x}{a}} \eta d\eta \int_{\xi-a\eta}^{\xi+a\eta} f(s) ds = \\ &= \frac{1}{2a^2} \int_{x-at}^x d\xi \int_{x-at}^{2\xi-x+at} (at-x+s)(at-x+2\xi-s) f(s) ds + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2a^2} \int_x^{x+at} d\xi \int_{2\xi-x-at}^{x+at} (at+x-s)(at-2\xi+x+s) f(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Oxirgi ikkita integralda ξ va s bo'yicha integrallash tartibini o'zgartiramiz va hosil bo'lgan ichki integrallarni hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \frac{1}{8a^2} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} (at-x+s)(at+x-s)^2 f(s) ds + \\ &+ \frac{1}{8a^2} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} (at+x-s)(at-x+s)^2 f(s) ds = \frac{t}{4a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2] f(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerdan (7) tenglikning to'g'riligi kelib chiqadi. Lemma isbotlandi.

{(1), (2)} masala yechimiga qaytaylik. [3] dan ma'lumki, (4) masalaning yechimi

$$U = \frac{1}{2a} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} f_1(s) ds + \frac{t}{4a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} f_2(s) ds \quad (8)$$

ko'rinishga ega, bu yerda

$$f_2(x) = \Phi_1(x) - a^2 f_1''(x). \quad (9)$$

U holda bu yechimni (3) masalaga qo'yib, {(1), (2)} masalaning yechimini yuqoridagi lemmaga asosan quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$u = \frac{1}{2a} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} \varphi_0(s) ds + \frac{t}{4a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} f_1(s) ds +$$

$$+\frac{t}{32a^3} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2] f_2(s) ds. \quad (10)$$

(8) va (10) tengliklarda $f_1(x)$ va $f_2(x)$ funksiyalar (5) va (9) tengliklar bilan aniqlanadi.

(10) ifodada

$$\frac{t}{4a} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} f_1(s) ds = \frac{1}{8a^3} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2] f_1(s) ds,$$

$$\frac{t}{32a^3} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2] f_2(s) ds = \frac{1}{128a^7} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2]^2 f_2(s) ds$$

ekanligini e'tiborga olsak, (10) umumiy yechimni quyidagicha yozish mumkinligi kelib chiqadi:

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=0}^2 \frac{1}{(2a)^{2k+1} (k!)^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} [(at)^2 - (x-s)^2]^k f_k(s) ds, \quad (11)$$

bu yerda

$$f_k(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j C_k^j a^{2j} \varphi_{k-j}^{(2j)}(x), \quad k = \overline{0,2} \quad (12)$$

va $C_k^j = k! / [j!(k-j)!]$ – binomial koeffitsiyent.

2-Koshi masalasi. Ω sohada (1) tenglamaning

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} u|_{t=0} = 0, \quad x \in R; \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi_0(x), \quad x \in R; \\ \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \Big|_{t=0} = 0, \quad x \in R; \quad \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial t^3} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi_1(x), \quad x \in R; \\ \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial t^4} \Big|_{t=0} = 0, \quad x \in R; \quad \frac{\partial^5 u}{\partial t^5} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi_2(x), \quad x \in R; \end{array} \right. \quad (13)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x,t) \in C^5(\Omega \cup J) \cap C^6(\Omega)$ yechimi topilsin, bu yerda $\psi_i(x)$, $i = \overline{0,2}$ – berilgan funksiyalar.

Matematik fizika tenglamalari nazariyasining superpozitsiya prinsipiga asosan {(1), (13)} masalaning U yechimi {(1), (2)} masalaning yechimini $(0,t)$ oraliqda integrallash natijasida hosil bo'ladi.

Demak,

$$U(x,t) = \int_0^t u(x,\eta) d\eta.$$

Bu yerda $u(x,t)$ funksiya (11) tenglik bilan aniqlanadi.

Demak, (1)-(13) masalaning umumiy yechimi

$$U(x,t) = \sum_{k=0}^2 \frac{1}{(2a)^{2k+1} (k!)^2} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} \left[(at)^2 - (x-s)^2 \right]^k g_k(s) ds \quad (14)$$

ko'rinishda bo'lar ekan, bu yerda

$$g_k(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j C_k^j a^{2j} \psi_{k-j}^{(2j)}(x), \quad k = \overline{0,2} \quad (15)$$

va $C_k^j = k! / [j!(k-j)!]$ – binomial koeffitsiyent.

3-Koshi masalasi. Ω sohada (1) tenglamaning

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} u|_{t=0} = \varphi_0(x), \quad x \in R; & \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi_0(x), \quad x \in R; \\ \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \Big|_{t=0} = \varphi_1(x), \quad x \in R; & \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial t^3} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi_1(x), \quad x \in R; \\ \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial t^4} \Big|_{t=0} = \varphi_2(x), \quad x \in R; & \frac{\partial^5 u}{\partial t^5} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi_2(x), \quad x \in R; \end{array} \right. \quad (16)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x,t) \in C^5(\Omega \cup J) \cap C^6(\Omega)$

yechimi topilsin, bu yerda $\varphi_i(x), \psi_i(x), i = \overline{0,2}$ – berilgan funksiyalar.

{(1), (16)} masalaning yechimi superpozitsiya prinsipiga asosan {(1), (2)} va {(1), (13)} masalalarning yechimlari yig'indisiga teng. Demak, (1)-(16) masalaning yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega:

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=0}^2 \frac{1}{(2a)^{2k+1} (k!)^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} \left[(at)^2 - (x-s)^2 \right]^k f_k(s) ds + \\ + \sum_{k=0}^2 \frac{1}{(2a)^{2k+1} (k!)^2} \int_{x-at}^{x+at} \left[(at)^2 - (x-s)^2 \right]^k g_k(s) ds, \quad (17)$$

bu yerda $f_k(x)$ va $g_k(x)$ funksiyalar (12) va (15) tengliklar bilan aniqlanadi.

Xususiyl holda, agar (1) tenglamada $a=1$ bo'lsa, $u_{ttttt} - 3u_{ttttx} + 3u_{ttxxx} - u_{xxxxx} = 0$ tenglamaning $u(x,0) = \varphi_0(x), u_t(x,0) = \psi_0(x), u_{tt}(x,0) = \varphi_1(x), u_{ttt}(x,0) = \psi_1(x), u_{tttt}(x,0) = \varphi_2(x)$ va $u_{ttttt}(x,0) = \psi_2(x)$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega ekanligi kelib chiqadi:

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=0}^2 \frac{1}{2^{2k+1} (k!)^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{x-t}^{x+t} [t^2 - (x-s)^2]^k f_k(s) ds + \\ + \sum_{k=0}^2 \frac{1}{2^{2k+1} (k!)^2} \int_{x-t}^{x+t} [t^2 - (x-s)^2]^k g_k(s) ds. \quad (18)$$

O'rniga qo'yish usuli bilan (11) funksiya {(1), (2)} masalaning, (14) funksiya {(1), (13)} masalaning va (17) funksiya {(1), (16)} masalaning yechimi ekanligini tekshirish qiyin emas.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI:

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